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Sessie 3C

Use of Information Technologies in Road Engineering: Detecting Damage Causes and Demonstration of a Thermal Line Scanner Analyzing Tool (SuPave)

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SuPAVE

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Introduction

- **Pavement**

Approximately covers 2% of our planet

- **Steps to pave a road**

Design

Preparation

Execution

- **Quality of the pavement**

Resistance to stresses and durability

Introduction

- **Advanced technologies**

Infrared Thermal Line-Scanner (IRTL)

Intelligent Roller Compactor (IRC)

Visual Inspection (VI)

- **Objective**

To find the relation between defects and paving operations

Methodology

- Test Track (located near the port of Antwerp-Bruges)

	Section 0	Section 1	Section 2	Section 3	Section 4
5 cm surface layer	SMA	APT-PoA	SMA	SMA	APT-V
2 x 8 cm base layer	APO-A	APO-A	APO-PoA	APO-PoA	APO-V
Base	20 cm unbound base geogrid 1: biaxial	20 cm unbound base geogrid 1: biaxial	20 cm unbound base geogrid 2: triaxial	25 cm lean asphalt (2 x 12,5 cm + tack coat)	25 cm lean asphalt (2 x 12,5 cm + tack coat)
	20 cm unbound base geogrid 1: biaxial	20 cm unbound base geogrid 1: biaxial	20 cm unbound base geogrid 2: triaxial	10 cm sub-base (granulates)	10 cm sub-base (granulates)
Subbase	Existing soil acts as the subbase (M1 > 35 MPa)				

Methodology

- Superimposing IRTL and IRC data and coring
- Volumetric properties (EN 12697-8)
- Dynamic modulus (EN 12697-26)
- Visual inspection

Results

■ Air voids ✓

■ Stiffness ✓

The screenshot shows the SuPave Dashboard interface. At the top right, there are icons for 'Fork', a refresh symbol, and a menu. The main heading is 'SuPave Dashboard'. Below it, a sub-heading reads: 'Upload your Excel file in the provided structure. If latitude/longitude is present, easting/northing will be ignored.' There is a button labeled '> Download input template'. A section titled 'Pave Quality Performance Indicators' is expanded, showing a list of indicators: 'TSI (Temperature Segregation Index): Max Temp - Mean Temp per distance bin. High TSI → higher risk of density variation.', 'DRS (Differential Range Statistics): T98.5 - T1 across width (robust range). High DRS → strong temperature spread/segregation.', 'Cold Risk: Cells below a fixed threshold (e.g., 120 °C). Indicates potential insufficient compaction and poorer bonding.', and 'Risk Area (Relative): Cells below a chosen % of the overall average temperature (default 90%). Highlights relative cold spots.' Below this, another instruction says: 'Upload your paving temperature file which follows the template format'. There is a file upload area with a cloud icon, the text 'Drag and drop file here', and a sub-note 'Limit 200MB per file • XLSX, XLS'. A 'Browse files' button is on the right. A light blue message box at the bottom of the upload area says 'Please upload an Excel file to proceed.' At the bottom right of the dashboard, there are icons for GitHub and a red button with a crown icon.

Fork

SuPave Dashboard

Upload your Excel file in the provided structure. If latitude/longitude is present, easting/northing will be ignored.

> Download input template

▼ Pave Quality Performance Indicators

- **TSI (Temperature Segregation Index):** Max Temp - Mean Temp per distance bin. High TSI → higher risk of density variation.
- **DRS (Differential Range Statistics):** T98.5 - T1 across width (robust range). High DRS → strong temperature spread/segregation.
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Upload your paving temperature file which follows the template format

Drag and drop file here
Limit 200MB per file • XLSX, XLS

Browse files

Please upload an Excel file to proceed.

Conclusion

- Volumetric and mechanical properties satisfied the standard requirements regardless of paving temperature and the number of roller passes.
- Compaction temperature plays a critical role, and surpassing the required range can compromise pavement performance and result in cracking.
- Utilizing advanced/smart technologies is a promising approach since such technologies can provide new insight into the pavement's performance and durability.
- Drilling more cores would be useful to genuinely determine the influence of paving operations on mixture performance via some statistical analysis.
- Long-term monitoring is required for a better understanding of the correlation between paving operations and pavement durability.

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Thank you for your attention

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